

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

PROGRESS OF COVID-19 EPIDEMIC IN PAKISTANDr Muhammad Anees Amin¹, Dr Shamsheer Haider², Dr Rimsha Mukhtar³^{1,2}Abbottabad International Medical College.³Hebei North University, Zhangjiakou China**Article Received:** August 2020**Accepted:** August 2020**Published:** September 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: The history of corona virus family is very old, it begins in 1965 when Tyrrell and Bynoe found that there was a virus family who damage the respiratory pathway. **Objectives:** The main objective of the study is to analyse the progress of COVID-19 pandemic in Pakistan. **Material and methods:** This cross sectional was conducted in Abbottabad International Medical College during March 2020 to May 2020. The data was collected through social media, mass media and by preparing a questionnaire. The data was collected for the analysis of COVID-19 spread and its causes in Pakistan. The data was collected and analysed by using Microsoft Excel 2017. **Results:** According to Pakistan's last update at 9:17 AM on June 119,536 confirmed coronavirus cases were reported in Pakistan. Out of this 119,536 almost 78,789 confirmed cases and 2356 deaths are occurred and 38,391 recoveries. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that COVID-19 is widely spreading in Pakistan. However, if we take one step toward self-isolation, it could save the entire community and the risk will decline immediately.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Muhammad Anees Amin,**

Abbottabad International Medical College.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Muhammad Anees Amin *et al*, **Progress Of COVID-19 Epidemic In Pakistan**, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2020; 07(09).

INTRODUCTION:

The history of corona virus family is very old, it begins in 1965 when Tyrrell and Bynoe found that there was a virus family who damage the respiratory pathway. This virus was named as B814 in that time. It was transmitted from animals to humans. Now, in 2020 there is a virus COVID-19 which is also belongs to the family of corona virus is infected the whole world. People all around the world facing the situation of pandemic. This virus effected the whole world and do not believe in racism¹.

COVID-19 is basically a medium size RNA virus and the nucleic acid is about 30 kb long, positive in sense, single stranded and polyadenylated. The RNA which is found in this virus is the largest known RNA and codes for a large polyprotein. In addition, coronaviruses are capable of genetic recombination if 2 viruses infect the same cell at the same time².

The most common symptoms of COVID-19 is cold, flu, fever and infection in lungs. There are different stages in the attacking of this virus. At stage one and at the start patient just feel flu and temperature just like common cold and flu³. But after seven days it becomes more worse and patient feels shortness of breath and dry cough. At advanced stage the patients become also suffered from pneumonia. There is no vaccine and antiviral therapy until now⁴.

In this short communication we will talk about current situation of COVID-19 in Pakistan. It was basically starting from China from December 2019, when there was a person who died in Wuhan (a city of China) due to an unknown virus. What started as an epidemic mainly limited to China has now become a truly global pandemic. There have now been over 392,331 confirmed cases and 17,156 deaths, according the John Hopkins University Covid-19 dashboard, which collates information from national and international health authorities. The disease has been detected in more 196 countries and territories, with Italy, the US and Spain experiencing the most widespread outbreaks outside of China. There were 438,441 cases from which 19,650 died and 111,877 were recovered all around the world⁵.

But now if we talk about Pakistan, we can easily find that it effects all the provinces of Pakistan. Until now (25th March 2020) there is 1013 confirmed cases of corona virus in Pakistan. From all confirmed cases there is 7 deaths reported till to date. It effects all the areas of Pakistan especially KPK, Gilgit Baltistan and Karachi. Almost 400 cases were reported from Sindh and it considered to be the most hitting part of the country. Pakistan banned all the national and international flights and Government supposed to be the situation of partial lock down in the country⁴.

According to media news, there were 300 cases from Punjab and 78 from KPK. Government urges the people to be self-quarantine themselves to fight coronavirus. But now here is the question of poverty, what poor people can do? Is there any help for poor and needy families? What daily wages people can do for their families? This is really a heart-breaking situation in Pakistan. Putting the country under lockdown would mean that my daily-wage workers, street vendors, small shop-owners would be locked inside their homes. But at this moment government announces some packages for daily wages and poor families. This seems very good and positive initiative for Pakistan.

Objectives

The main objective of the study is to analyse the progress of COVID-19 pandemic in Pakistan.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross sectional was conducted in Abbottabad International Medical College during March 2020 to May 2020. The data was collected through social media, mass media and by preparing a questionnaire. The data was collected for the analysis of COVID-19 spread and its causes in Pakistan.

The data was collected and analysed by using Microsoft Excel 2017.

RESULTS:

According to Pakistan's last update at 9:17 AM on June 119,536 confirmed coronavirus cases were reported in Pakistan. Out of this 119,536 almost 78,789 confirmed cases and 2356 deaths are occurred and 38,391 recoveries.

The data of provinces are shown in table 01.

Table 01: COVID-19 data according to provinces

	Confirmed Cases	Active Cases	Deaths	Recoveries
AJK	2,566	214	70	2,282
Balochistan	14,607	1,255	145	13,207
GB	3,542	371	83	3,088
Islamabad	16,246	437	180	15,629
KPK	37,418	419	1,258	35,741
Punjab	98,602	1,216	2,227	95,159
Sindh	134,437	3,158	2,469	128,810

Graphical representation of daily outbreak of COVID-19 in Pakistan

DISCUSSION:

There were some preventive measures which is necessary to win this battle in Pakistan. The most important thing is to wash your hands properly for 20 seconds, use sanitizers and stay away from infected people. Use masks and gloves and do not leave the house until it becomes very necessary⁵. The army has said it will open all military hospitals and health facilities nationwide to assist in testing and treating virus cases. The most important thing is to be calm and pray for the better situation because there is a must win battle for Pakistan. As a nation it becomes our duty to protect our country, nation and ourselves. We hope for the better condition in our country as well as around the globe⁶.

With increasing cases of immensely contagious COVID-19, Pakistan's economy is under great deterioration. The terror of fatal disease and economic distress have come up together. The country cannot bear extended lockdown and should

the lockdown extend, Pakistan will suffer unmanageable economic loss. Pakistan does not have any sufficient resources to provide for the patients at the moment. Most of the populace is working on daily wages. The shutdown of the whole country would cause death either due to hunger or from COVID-19. The current statement of Pakistan's prime minister calls for a community meeting among susceptible countries that are dealing with the pandemic. It has been decided that rather than complete shutdown, people should avoid mass gatherings, and partial shutting down of the country will take place in order for the economy to provide for basic necessities⁷.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that COVID-19 is widely spreading in Pakistan. However, if we take one step toward self-isolation, it could save the entire community and the risk will decline immediately. This is a situation where each individual has to take steps

toward minimizing the risk by staying in the house and immobilizing themselves.

REFERENCES:

1. World Health Organization. Pakistan: COVID-19—Situation update as of 7 April 2020 (3:00 pm). Updates: Ministry of National Health Services Regulations and Coordination Dashboard; 2020.
2. Wang C, Horby PW, Hayden FG, Gao GF. A novel coronavirus outbreak of global health concern. *Lancet*. 2020;395(10223):470-473. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30185-9
3. Shi Z, Hu Z. A review of studies on animal reservoirs of the SARS coronavirus. *Virus Res*. 2008;133(1):74-87. doi:10.1016/j.virusres.2007.03.012
4. Pakistan confirms first two cases of coronavirus. <https://www.france24.com/en/20200226-pakistanconfirms-first-two-cases-of-coronavirus>. Accessed March 31, 2020.
5. Ahmed T. NIBD set to treat COVID-19 patients through passive immunisation. <https://tribune.com.pk/story/2194441/1-nidb-set-treat-covid-19-patients-passive-immunisation/>. Accessed April 15, 2020.
6. Wrapp D, Wang N, Corbett KS, et al. Cryo-EM structure of the 2019-nCoV spike in the prefusion conformation. *2020;1263(March):1260-1263*.
7. Impact of COVID-19 on economy of Pakistan. <https://www.brecorder.com/2020/03/28/584351/impact-of-covid-19-on-economy-of-pakistan/>. Accessed April 18, 2020.